

EMPIRICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL ISSUES ABOUT VOCATIONAL TRAINING AND PEDAGOGICAL GUIDANCE

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ABSTRACT

This work is intended to reflect on empirical, theoretical, philosophical and psychosocial aspects, particularly foundations, which support the process of professional training and educational professional guidance. An excursion into historical materialism, which reveals the role to be played by education and counseling for children, adolescents and young people, not only in professional training and professional teaching guidance based on the teacher's personal example and other conditions; but in the training and preparation for life of the younger generation in general. This is a bibliographical research, based on classic Cuban authors who focus on the understanding and empirical learning of the theme. Vocational guidance is not a proposal free of interests of all kinds, much less as subjective as it can be presented to those who benefit from it. The advisor's work consists of leading the spirit of young people to the paths that can best meet, in a pragmatic way, the aspirations and needs of the nation. When this precept is removed from the power of the State, leaving each one to follow the direction of his life, according to his most legitimate desires, in a short time, there is the collapse of the principles that until then sustained that society and its destiny closest is slavery. It is concluded that the psychosocial foundations of education and guidance represent the bases of the process of professional training and teaching of professional guidance, as it is conceived in the very process of personality formation and the type of guidance presented.

Keywords: Vocational training. Pedagogical orientation. Professional orientation. Life project.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of education is reflected in society from the moment it presents educational training requirements and requirements and specific actions that have empirical conditions to respond to the training requirements of an individual model that meets the economic needs of

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a country and that defends the values and ideals of the social class that the government represents, that is, a pragmatic individual.

In socialist society, formal education is expressed with a view to

To educate new generations and all people in the scientific world, fully develop the individual's intellectual, physical and spiritual capabilities, and encourage him to high human feelings and aesthetic taste; convert ideological-political and communist morality into personal beliefs, habits of principles of daily conduct, form a free man to live and participate actively and consciously in the construction of socialism and communism (MINED Group, 2012, p. 20).

It is inferred from the above statement that formal education responds to certain types of socio-economic training, considering that it responds to the needs and requirements of building social capital, through the training of its citizens. In this context, education and guidance in general processes and professional training and professional guidance and teaching in particular, have a common philosophical and psychological basis, because all these aspects are based on a common principle, the integral and pragmatic formation of man.

The interest, with such proposal, is to have a society that acts in favor of improving the dynamic processes of life and the mechanisms of production of essential goods and services. For this to happen, individuals must be, in a way, fulfilled and satisfied with their decisions, which does not always happen, because existence poses a range of challenges that only a few can overcome.

It is in this space that the concern with professional vocational guidance is inserted, considering that the social investment in relation to a student is very high, this in terms of market expectations, occupation, economic return, in the form of providing first-class services needs and the required quality.

Formal education has been trying to take this space, not because it is an obligation or merit; but it has done so, on the grounds that everyone should have the freedom to make a subjective choice, which conflicts with the work of the advisor, in which after applying a battery of tests, all of them objective, their interpretation is, strictly, subjectively, and what we have is nothing more than a reduction in the dimension of symbolic family violence over the interests of the children, in which this is transferred to an agent of the State who claims to be impartial in his guidelines.

PHILOSOPHICAL FOUNDATIONS OF EDUCATION AND PEDAGOGICAL GUIDANCE

Historical materialism asserts that the entire socio-economic formation (ESF) consists, in an essential way, of a mode of production, particularly in its internal structure, for the development of the productive forces and of the relations of production and property established in the means themselves. of production. If the mode of production is socialist, then ownership of the major means of production will be in the hands of the state. An almost opposite fact occurs, in the sense that, if the mode of production is capitalist, then the ownership of the large means of production will be distributed in the hands of entrepreneurs (large, small and micro) and the State will also hold sectors of production, so that he can regulate, when this proves necessary, and control prices, since, as he is also a producer, he knows the cost-benefit ratio of the production of goods.

In the structure of the mode of production, a dialectical relationship is revealed between the development of the productive forces and the relations of production, which are conditioned and presuppose each other. These relationships determine the way of life and manifest themselves in the psychological aspects of people, expressed in ways of thinking and acting. Likewise, the mode of production shapes society's ideology and values, an ideology that people have, regardless of their will, their religious beliefs; and such conjunctures end up conditioning forms of social consciousness, that is, the mode of production is the basis on which the entire superstructure of society is built and maintained.

In this sense, Federico Engels argues that,

The materialist conception of history starts from the thesis that production, and with it the exchange of its products, is the basis of the entire social order; and that, in all societies that parade throughout history, there is the distribution of products, as well as the social division into classes or properties and is governed by what is produced and how it is produced and the way of exchanging the product (ENGELS, 1979, p. 325).

What Engels wants to say is that the product and the form of production determine the ways of life of any society, even considering the mechanical solidarity system ²⁸. Does he place an arbitrary force on this system of production, and to what extent does this merit extend over the vocational decision of school-aged individuals?

²⁸In the conception of Emilè Durkheim (1433-1502 dH) the mechanical solidarity in a society goes beyond the sum of individuals (their individual consciences), it is constituted in the collective conscience . It is present in societies that are primitive or pre-capitalist, considered simpler, *such* as, for example, indigenous tribes (Authors' Note, 2023).

Obviously, a society has to worry about its economic survival and, based on this detail, it needs production mechanisms that guarantee it as competitive and, within this scope that, at first glance, seems to be trivial, but which proves to be very deep and highly complex, because the main product it has to market represents its standard of excellence and, as a consequence, of existence, as a nation. Hence the need for young people to be guided about their professional future, because the interest in question is not private, it is national.

Hence, vocational guidance is not a proposal free of interests of all kinds, much less as subjective as it can be presented to those who benefit from it. The advisor's work consists of leading the spirit of young people to the paths that can best meet, in a pragmatic way, the aspirations and needs of the nation. When this precept is removed from the power of the State, leaving each one to follow the direction of his life, according to his most legitimate desires, in a short time, there is the collapse of the principles that until then sustained that society and its destiny closest is slavery.

In capitalist production systems, competition marks the constant development of new ideas and products, in which intelligence has to be constantly shown through creativity, given that there is a whole race to please the customer and offer him conditions of comfort and well-being, according to what you are willing to pay for it.

In the social ownership of the means of production, which characterizes the socialist mode of production, as F. Engels has pointed out,

The ability to guarantee to all members of society, through social production, an existence that, in addition to being rewarding every day, fully and more easily satisfies their material needs, but also ensures the development and fulfillment of their physical and spiritual capacities freely and fully, this possibility was achieved for the first time today and only today has it really been achieved (ENGELS, 1979, p. 325).

Specific processes and conditions of historical, sociocultural and socioeconomic life of the people are those that go through the whole process of formation and development of the individual and collective personality. Personality has historical-social conditioning; in this sense, there is a dialectical triad between education, economic development and socio-historical personality conditioning. It is then that education and guidance come into play, accounting for their role in forming this model of man that society needs, to respond to the demands of economic development, bearer of society's values, capable of defending its principles.

FUNDAMENTALS OF PSYCHOSOCIAL EDUCATION AND COUNSELING

The fundamental unit of the course of human life are themes marked and substantiated by existential events, which can be described and represented through any psychological event that is produced by the interaction of a subjective vector (needs, motivations, desires, projects, personal resources, etc.), confronted with an objective vector (external reality, physical, social, cultural, etc.) that the person can take as a *leitmotif* for the individual determination for a positive or negative valence. In the confrontation between these two vectors, if the result of valence is positive, the result is success, achievement of goals, fulfillment and personal satisfaction; on the contrary, if the result of the valence is negative, the feeling expressed is frustration, difficulties, obstacles, failure. In this sense, the individual will have to look for compensatory mechanisms, substitutions or alterations that replace his target desire.

The problem of training in education reveals that students should not be thought of and interpreted as isolated phenomena from the concrete situations in which they arise, but, above all, be studied, taking into account cause and effect and that their emergence originates from of a social historical conditioning, because, the problems of formation and development of the structure of the personality, of the way of life and the established relationships, except in cases of pathologies can be: Education and culture; Ideological and moral education; Psychology; Interpersonal relationships and personal social adaptation and the formation of a scientific world

This is where you can play a leadership role as a teacher guiding students in solving their problems. These that are related to a set of psychosocial factors, such as living conditions, working conditions, stress levels, social support, lifestyle and coping strategies that can affect the mental unit and mental health individually and collective. When José Martí (1853-1895) stated that to educate is to prepare man for life, he was expressing, in a very wise way, guidance purposes, because in its semantic sense, to educate is to discipline, guide, guarantee the due social commitment to the generation, the traditions and socio-economic principles of a given nation.

Torroella (1990) defined the orientation and help that is offered to the individual as a variety of techniques that help him with the physical, psychological and moral development to his limits and to be able to apply his abilities in the sense of learning to study, work and life. come true in life.

Del Pino (1998) defines professional guidance as a

It helps in the relationship established with the student to facilitate the process of developing their professional identity, through different techniques and integrated into the general paths of the teaching process, depending on the evolutionary stage, the socio-political context and the specific situation in which they are involved. find (DEL PINO, 1998, p. 57).

The author puts it, in very broad terms, that professional vocation is a social construction that, in the current era, depends greatly on the figure of the teacher, considering that he has become a substitute for the father and mother in the intimate life of the child. The relationships defined between the internal and external processes of existence are conditioned by the school curriculum and the pedagogical creativity of teachers.

This teaching system that has been adopted, which transforms the student into an intellectual eunuch, distances him from the empirical experience of things, preventing him from feeling in conflict with certain fields of knowledge and, thus, devoid of any possibility of clash, chooses what seems to be the most economically profitable; however, he does so in the absence of a *pathos* that leads him to an erotic relationship with the chosen career and this ends up creating a generation of people unhappy with their choices and, moreover, with the guidance received from their masters.

Manzano and Torres (2013) define Professional Training and professional guidance as

A process that occurs throughout people's lives, starting in childhood and extending throughout their professional lives. It is, therefore, conceived as part of a permanent education of the subject's personality, which prepares for training and professional performance in a responsible manner (Idem, 2013, p. 89).

Given what these authors express, it can be inferred that professional training and professional guidance promote the formation and development of personality with a professional intentionality; it is part of the guidance for the development of children, adolescents and young people towards a proactive life, related to their future profession.

This empirical link with the future profession is what must be sought in a solid process of vocational guidance, because it is there that the individual will spend the rest of his existence, thinking, dreaming, creating, innovating, learning and teaching, while applying his technique in solving increasingly complex and challenging problems. Depriving the advisee of this condition of proximity to what could be his act of future existence is the right step for the discontinuities in higher education courses that he is faced with at universities.

Thus, the role of the vocational guidance counselor is not theoretical, in the sense of interpreting an endless number of answers that make no sense to the student. Their work must be based on an empirical agenda, with the development and fulfillment of tasks, under the

observation of a tutor, didactically prepared to continue explaining to candidates the potential, possibilities and also the difficulties inherent in each profession.

Throughout the process, students can discover vocations for fields of knowledge parallel to the professions under analysis and, when this happens, there is a conflict, which makes the decision for a healthier career, because there is now the need for studies around them. The indecision in relation to the professional choice, which is a sublimation of the conflict, is what makes others, within the collective, decide first and be satisfied with such a choice.

The orientation is rooted in the main objectives of the new pedagogy, which aims at the full, harmonious and pragmatic development of man, in which he defends that he proves himself and proves useful to society. Its doctrine emphasizes knowledge, respect and cultivation of the students' personality, autonomy, self-regulation, their freedom of creation, as well as social responsibility, where the close relationship between education and guidance is observed.

When the idea of a harmonious development is highlighted, this does not imply the absence of any kind of conflict, because to think and believe in this way is to demonstrate, in an empirical way, complete ignorance about the human being and his personological state and to let oneself be carried away by folly. That the ideal man is the one who does not get involved in the battle for the pursuit of the ideal. Were the human being, absent from any type of conflict, of all nature, guidance would prove unnecessary.

The objectives of the orientation are presented in:

- ✓ Promotion and development of personality, promoting basic learning for life;
- ✓ Prevention of loss of mental health;
- ✓ Facilitation of development tasks;
- ✓ I help the subject in problematic situations at different stages of life;
- ✓ Help people in critical situations, depression, conflicts, etc.;
- ✓ Training the individual to help himself (TORROELLA, 1990).

Guidance is a professional service that aims to help students who have learning problems by carrying out a set of tasks that enable them to reach their maximum development, subject to their respective potential conditions, which can be performance boosters, limiters, to highlight, age, economic factors, motivation, enthusiasm.

It should be noted that guidance, although it acts efficiently on the bottlenecks that are preventing the *normal development* of students, it does not provide students with means to solve problems and difficulties; rather, it seeks to develop in these individuals a general ability to

understand their problems and difficulties, how to admit, tolerate, solve and make decisions for themselves; this implies that they are put into practice with a minimum of conflict.

Among the types of guidance we can mention:

1. Developmental orientation: Promotes optimal personality development by creating conditions conducive to effective learning and age-appropriate developmental tasks (preventive);

2. Consultative or reparation guidance: aimed at helping individuals and/or groups, so that the failures present in the execution of tasks of their age must be eliminated, through guidance actions that act on the root causes (TORROELLA , nineteen ninety).

With regard to the response arising from the guidance arising from the areas of application, Torroella (1990) states that they can be: educational advice, professional guidance, personal guidance, social guidance and vital guidance.

According to the consulted literature, Daudinot (2013, p. 10) reports that

Vocational Guidance has its origins in 1908 with the creation, in Boston (USA), of the first Bureau of Vocational Guidance by F. Parsons, who coined the term Vocational Guidance, designed to help young people who required help in choosing a career and orient yourself in the professional world.

According to the systematization of studies, it was Fitch who, in 1935, published his book on *Vocational Guidance* (OP), where he states that it is defined as “the process of individual assistance for the selection of an occupation, preparation for it, initiation and development in it” (Op. Cit.).

The concept presented, in this epigraph, shows that, from the moment a profession is chosen, a whole set of developmental actions is necessary to reach the ends that were proposed, with the initial action. It is an individual technical investment that goes beyond simply choosing an occupation; it is a destination to follow and a path to be followed, towards a future, both individually and collectively.

This awareness that the object choices of present life are not as autonomous as presumed is the first step towards understanding the political positions that belong to each young person, still in the student course and, what has been fostered, in recent times is a condition from trying to solve the issues that human beings have been through since prehistoric times (environmental, social, economic) with forceps, as if those who preceded the current generation had not tried it or that they had neglected all the symptoms that are shown to be urgent in be treated and healed.

What is clear is that vocational guidance will follow the parameters and political guidelines that guide social thinking at the given moment of its application to the target audience who are interested in providing guidance regarding a professional career. Without realizing it, all individuals end up involved in the theme that is based on human need, at very specific moments, to highlight, when faced with strong weather conditions and this requires creative engineers who provide the construction of efficient and effective barriers against the elements. and the fury of nature, the State directs all of its *marketing* force to the training of engineers in various fields, giving scholarships , motivation to students who stand out in the fields of Physics and Mathematics and even those who prove to be talented in other fields of knowledge, but who show high reasoning ability. So, economics and politics are the determining factors within the field of guidance for vocational training.

Del Pino (1998), referring to the interpretation of the genesis of the professional training process, makes it based on a classification of three trends that are summarized as follows:

1. The first trend suggests that vocation is innate, that it is born with it and cannot be changed.
2. The second tendency expresses that the vocation is created or can be given directly.
3. The third tendency has as arguments, that the vocation can be built, in shape, activated in a creative way through the subjectivity of the subject, says that it is mutable, it is not absolute and are implicit in it, different alternatives (DEL PINO, 1998, p. 57).

Of the three alternatives presented for professional vocation, none of them addresses the issue that the pressing need for manpower is what determines, in fact, a significant portion of the results obtained. Key sectors of the economy tend to collapse if their urgencies are not attended to by specialized personnel, something that the school, in the current mold, is not able to attend, but that the market itself takes care of solving through its processes of continuous formation and actions intermittent, stages, among others.

It is very complex for someone who does not have a vocation for a certain area without even having experienced it as part of his creativity, that is, without knowing what he might think and how to act when in contact with real situations that challenge him to overcome its limitations. This is one of the most interesting points of professional guidance, in which candidates who are under *observation* are subjected to situations that provoke them to find inner resources in directions that, until that very moment, did not arouse any passion or motivation in them. The experience with the target object is what leads the individual to ecstasy and finds himself prepared to assume such field of knowledge as his own, even without, before that intimate contact, there was no reciprocal interest.

Believing that vocation is something innate is surrendering to the idyllic and unusual thoughts of Plato (842-762 AH) believing that all human knowledge is, in the same way, innate; which is a crass error, because the creativity that is the manifestation of intelligence, once applied to problem situations posed by society, is improved every time it is faced with a new challenge and innovates based on them. If the vocation was innate, in some specific field, would the effort that the student would have to learn the concepts of that *sui generis* knowledge system of each area and apprehend them, would it be less? Defenders of such an idea would say yes...; but they do not present real situations, given that even extremely successful professionals in their respective fields even failed at certain times in their academic and working lives.

If the vocation were created, providing it directly to the individual under guidance would create a paradox, without conditions of any solutions to it; because this could be interpreted as *forceps imposition*. The author presents it as a direct product of economics and politics; but it reduces the element of surprise to tyrannical action by superiors on students. And, this is not exactly how the machine works, the *establishment* does not work freely with its impositions, leaving them in the illusion of individual and collective subjectivity; in fact, the latter is the most efficient mechanism to lead the individual will to the State's interest.

The author makes a mistake when he says that a vocation can be built; because it is always the product of the interest of a society or a nation. Social demands are what will determine the directions that pedagogues and vocational guidance counselors will direct their speeches. In the wake, he clarifies that a whole set of possibilities is presented to the individual, so that his will extends until he reaches the scope of the search for the profession that he believes to be his innate vocation.

Del Pino and Manzano (2009) define career guidance teaching as a

System of educational influences aimed at stimulating the pedagogical vocation in students, admission to careers with a profile and retention of their development. It should include student assistance in the complex process of defining their life project, taking into account the social priority (Idem, p. 56).

Here, the author clarifies that, vocational guidance definitely leads to the State's need to train qualified labor in order to meet its most pressing interests. This is an issue that is sometimes implied in discussions in which the intention is to place individual interest far above the collective interest, which generates conflicts that are difficult to resolve, because, for example, a Formula 1 racer and an ace soccer player can bring immense joy to his country and the nation, which is not disputed; but what is its social role in the production of direct consumer goods?

In any nation, the choice for sports is almost always free; however, in socialist countries, where everyone contributes directly to the nation's wealth, these individual athletes do so peremptorily; because the goods they conquer, through their efforts, belong to the nation of which they are a part and, thus, the economic gains obtained will be distributed among all; not just the joy of victory and conquest.

In capitalist systems, in which everyone is sovereign over their individual conquests, the State encourages young people, from an early age, to choose professions of a pragmatic nature, because the interest is in the production of currency for the nation. None of this is printed on *billboards* along the main avenues of a city; however, the subjective message is of collective and not private interest.

How are the stage of development of life projects and personality constructed?

The main stages of personality development are:

1. Early Childhood:

- Infant (0 to 1 year old)
- Early age (1 to 3 years old)
- Preschool (from 3 to 6 years old)

2. Age - school (6 to 12 years old)

3. Teenagers (11-12 to 15-16 years old)

4. Young age (16 to 20 years old).

The youthful age is the one that deserves more attention in relation to the rest of the other stages, considering that it is at this stage that young people feel the need to build their individual and collective life project. This work is recognized as not enough and that professional guidance is a general integrated personality formation, with an intentionality that starts from the process of earlier ages.

Professional Guidance is a job developed in terms of careers to advise the family, which, sometimes, is not aware of certain professions; he is the one who guides the young person to select a certain profession or trade, continues to look for offers and requests for employment related to the economic and social needs of the country. Sometimes, deciding on the imposed future, or better, proposing a professional life project, which is more similar to what they want, demonstrating there that it is not always what the children want and what the family wants. either for their own children.

The basic needs of youth are:

1. Autonomy of conduct, moral and economic;
2. Formation of a scientific world;
3. Meaning of life;
4. Construction of the life project.

Faced with the four pedagogical situations posed, the one that, in fact, is incumbent upon the school is the construction of a scientific world; however, she has taken the life project as her master activity guiding the student's professional life, which is a crass error, given that a decision of such magnitude, which implies investments of various kinds, from the economic to the libidinal, this action is something that would be within the family's scope of action and, it, indirectly, would fulfill the role of the State.

THE LEADING ACTIVITY: SELECTION OF PROFESSION OR OCCUPATION

In order for the Professional Guidance activity to become relevant, it is necessary to define the action that guides it through the process towards what is intended as the end for which it is intended. For D'Angelo Hernandez (2004), this is characterized as a life project and is defined as

Welcoming the person in their essential dimensionality of life, a perspective of ideal management of a complex real model about your life, what you expect or want to be and do, which materializes in the real layout and reach internal and external possibilities; defines his relationship with the world and with himself, his reason for being as an individual in a context and type of a given society (D'ÂNGELO HERNANDEZ, 2004, p. 133).

The aforementioned author points out that life projects are formed based on the determination of material conditions and spiritual life, expressing the individual's active influence on society as a character, the projection of their experiences and life actions in different areas of collective activity. It also highlights that the construction of life projects occurs through the double determination of the relationship between the individual and society as a manifestation of the social essence of the concrete individual.

In response to these reasons, D'Angelo (2004) says that if life projects are considered from the dialectical relations between the individual and society, in the determination of the individual and his projection to society; then, they can be investigated as psychological training of individuals in their social context and can also be analyzed as a macro social phenomenon;

as a manifestation of the relationship between individual and social consciousness, which can be interpreted as two levels of expression of life projects.

D'Angelo Hernandez states the following:

The life project and psychological formation of the personality that integrates the main life directions implies, on the one hand, the relationships of all the person's social activities (work, profession, family, free time, socio-political, interpersonal cultural relationships of friendship and love, organizational; otherwise, it is the expression of the functioning of the different mechanisms and psychological formations that make up the entire field of personal experience) (D'ANGELO HERNANDEZ, 2004, p. 137).

Taking this speech, what is exposed is that the life project is the leading activity, as it is the most complex that involves human existence, ranging from an object choice, defined by desire, to the consummation of this choice, based on the particular conditions of the individual. Thus, it becomes a sensitive field for the advisor to act on and which, in most cases, end in disasters and frustrations, exactly, due to lack of knowledge or not considering these details.

As for professional training and professional educational guidance, the author defines them as:

The system of educational and assistance influences received by the student by the teacher, for the construction of the life project, as a result of the teaching of professional motivation maintained in the process of training and development of his personality (D'ANGELO HERNANDEZ, 2004, p. 45).

Some methodological issues that can be considered for the work are the advantages of the work of professional teaching guidance, unlike other professions, are in the natural environment where teaching, the professional activity takes place is the school or educational institution, where students have direct and daily experience (positive - negative) and that teachers have a direct influence on the student as primary role models.

Del Pino and Manzano (2009) propose the following dimensions to carry out the work of teaching professional guidance:

1. The political commitment of those involved
2. Specialized preparation and methodological, institutional strength
3. Presence of pedagogical models at school
4. Scientific direction of work.

They proposed in the methodological obligations that must be considered in the development of the work of professional training and educational professional guidance, which complement to increase the dimensions of the work of guidance raised by Del Pino and Manzano (2009). These are:

- ✓ Be an example: The teacher or teachers must possess certain professional qualities and personality traits that set them apart and distinguish them from other members of society, serving as a role model for their students.
- ✓ Diagnosis: From students, parents, pedagogical collective of the school or educational institution, board of directors, community and personnel services. It is necessary to identify the strengths and weaknesses of each and every one of the actors that are part of it and determine the development of the educational process.
- ✓ The organization of the teaching process: Analyzing the school rules, regulations, employment contracts, teaching schedule, teaching, effective and extension teachers, planning all activities carried out, ensuring the material base for study and life, etc.
- ✓ Develop learning and development tasks: Meaning of a development of the teaching-learning process from its theoretical and practical bases, learning tasks and self-development of age, level of education or type.
- ✓ Political preparation, methodological and scientific teaching: Develop an improvement in teacher training where the system conceives the methodological work plan of the school or institution, which reflect the preparation in political issues, which are collected in the individual work plans and in the development plans , participation in scientific events for teacher-students, etc.
- ✓ Self-coaching: A teacher needs to have enough space to deepen the content of his teaching object or activity to be developed over time, it must be a constant to achieve quality in the process.
- ✓ Control and demand: Checks of the management process, of the educational process in the school or educational institution, requires that they be carried out and the results of the work evaluated. It allows *feedback* and demand to ensure that the planned activities are carried out and the proposed objectives are achieved.

These conditions are present throughout the institutional management process at different levels of specificity: board of directors, technical assistance, scientific consultancy,

teaching departments or chairs, collective careers or specialties, collective discipline, group of the year, subject collectives, classes.

This for the connotation of the example of the teacher for the student, as a model to work efficiently and to develop professional training and educational professional guidance and educational work in general, must possess certain qualities that characterize it.

But, what qualities should a teacher have to develop the work of school and professional pedagogical guidance?

✓ Qualities a teacher should have:

1. Sociopolitics: Domain Philosophy, Ideological, being an example.

2. Psychological:

- ✓ Professional character traits: includes socio-political characteristics, mastery of his subject, creative character, and not admitting mistakes, demanding of himself, the critical attitude towards knowledge.
- ✓ Intellectual and pedagogical observation: Traits of Care, professional memory, developed language, developing thinking skills, know-how, pedagogical forecasts, developing your ideas and projections.
- ✓ Be disciplined, with volitional characteristics, security forces, initiative, organization and independence in your work; be courageous and firm, bring your activities to the end.
- ✓ Emotional traits: Be cheerful and optimistic, balanced, have control and know how to choose your phrases. Be kind, patient and have faith in others
- ✓ Traits in their relationships with students: Affinity with students, being communicative and friendly, attentive and concerned; to help.
- ✓ Socialist humanism: the ability to understand and easy to establish new relationships

3. Authority:

Conceives the true political and ideological conception and strong moral convictions. Love and respect for students, the mastery of knowledge he has. having broad culture

4. Pedagogical contact:

It is a reflection of the teacher's relationships with students, their parents and their own colleagues. Requirement of mutual respect and fairness in treatment.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The process of professional training and teaching of professional guidance responds to a materialist conception of history; it has a social historical conditioning that is determined by society's mode of production and social demands and needs.

2. Psychosocial foundations of Education and guidance are the bases of the process of professional training and teaching of professional guidance, as it is conceived in the very process of personality formation and the type of guidance presented.

3. To develop the work of professional training and educational professional guidance, it is necessary to take into account its proposed dimension and conditioning, evaluating the example of the teacher.

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